

ADDITIONAL DEMOGRAPHICS

Motivation to participate in chatrooms

Fig. 1: The relationship between the most recurrent themes of RQ1 and the demographics of our participants. Figure 1 shows how the (i) employment status, (ii) experience, and (iv) gender of our participants relate to the most recurrent themes of RQ1.

Regarding *employment status* (Figure 1a), we observe that *self employed* participants are mainly motivated by *giving back to the community*, *customer support*, and *personal gain*. These results conform with intuition, since self employed participants would likely wish to have a channel to reach his/her customers (customer support) while striving in his/her business (personal gain). Regarding *full time employees* and *students*, it is clear that the main motivator for using chatrooms is the *quality of help*. Indeed, both employees and students face deadlines, which would likely lead them to appreciate receiving high quality help.

With respect to *experience* (Figure 1b), we also observe an intuitive trend. Most experienced participants are mainly motivated by *giving back to the community*, whereas most inexperienced participants are motivated by receiving *fast responses* and *quality help*. It is also interesting to notice that participants who are in the middle in terms of experience are mainly motivated by *personal gains*, which is also intuitive as these participants would still be wishing to climb the ladders.

Regarding *gender* (Figure 1c), it is interesting to notice that female participants are mostly interested in the *internal communication*, while *male* participants are mainly interested in *giving back to the community*. However, more in-depth empirical studies need to be performed to verify whether this is indeed a trend.

Summary of the demographics of the 21 interviewees

Tables 1-4 below show a summary of the demographics of the 21 interviewees (8 from Slack and 13 from Gitter) in terms of experience, degrees, employment status, and roles in projects.

TABLE 1: Years of software development experience of interviewees in Slack and Gitter

Number of Years	Slack	Gitter
0 to 3	0	0
4	1	0
5	0	3
6	0	1
7	2	3
8	1	2
9	1	1
10 or more	3	3

TABLE 2: Highest earned degree of interviewees in Slack and Gitter

Degree	Slack	Gitter
Bachelor's	4	7
College Diploma	1	0
Doctorate	0	1
Master's	1	0
Other	0	0
Professional degree	2	2
Self-taught	0	3
Student	0	0

TABLE 3: Employment status of interviewees in Slack and Gitter

Degree	Slack	Gitter
Full-time	8	7
Other	0	0
Part-time	0	1
Self-employed	0	5
Student	0	0
Unemployed	0	0

TABLE 4: Project roles of interviewees in Slack and Gitter

Degree	Slack	Gitter
Active contributor	5	8
Maintainer	3	2
No active role	0	1
Occasional contributor	0	2
Other	0	0
User	0	0

Impact of chatrooms in the software project

Fig. 2: The relationship between the most recurrent themes of RQ2 and the demographics of our participants. Figure 2 shows how the (i) employment status, (ii) experience, and (iv) gender of our participants relate to the most recurrent themes of RQ2.

Regarding *employment status* (Figure 2a) it is interesting to observe how *self employed* participants mostly pay attention

to the *brainstorming of features*. This result may be explained by the fact that *self employed* participants strive for new and creative features to gain competitive advantage in their projects.

With respect to *experience* (Figure 2b), we observe that less experienced participants perceive that *access to information* and *feature brainstorming* are the major impacts that chatrooms have in the projects, whereas more experienced participants stress that *issue resolution* and *tasks* are the aspects that are mostly impacted. This observation hints that the perceived impact might be biased towards the motivation of participants. For example, since the least experienced participants are mostly motivated by receiving help, they perceive that the greatest impact is the *access to information*.

Regarding *gender* (Figure 2c), we again notice a trend of female participants to notice the communication aspects of the project. For example female participants perceive that the strongest impacts are related to *brainstorming features*. Female participants are also a majority when stressing the *access to information* and *group awareness* (which are also related to communication). However, the difference in perceptions between male and female participants is not as large in terms of *access to information* and *group awareness*. We also observe, that male participants perceive that the *issue resolution process* is the most impacted by the use of chatrooms. Nevertheless, we acknowledge that more in-depth research has to be carried to better analyze the differences associated to gender.

Perceived Quality of Chatrooms

When it comes to *employment status* (Figure 3a), we observe that *self employed* participants emphasize on the quality of the *community*. This is intuitive as people working on autonomous projects would likely benefit the most from very active and helpful communities. We also notice that *full time* and *part time* employees tend to emphasize on the *improvement of features* in chatrooms. Considering our results from RQ3, this is likely due to the lack of a robust historical search in chatrooms, which causes the loss of information and knowledge (e.g., as stated by participant G23).

Regarding *experience* (Figure 3b), we note that very experienced participants (i.e., 10+ years of experience) praise the *community* aspect of chatrooms. We speculate that this is likely due to the feeling of “giving back to the community” that we observe in RQ1. Experienced participants may have received substantial help in the past, which likely drives them to praise the good quality of a community. As for less experienced participants (0-4 years of experience), the focus is on the *improvement of features*. We suspect that less experienced participants have a mindset set more towards productivity (so they can climb the ladders more quickly), which influences their perceptions regarding feature improvements. It is interesting to notice that moderately experienced participants (5-9 years of experience) have stressed the importance of *moderation* in chatrooms. This might be because such participants might not have reached a position of leadership yet, but already appreciate what a good leadership is, which leads them to stress on the importance of a proper moderation of the chatrooms.

As for the *gender* aspect, the clearest distinction is regarding *moderation*, where female participants tend to emphasize on *moderation* more than the male participants. We suspect that this might be reflective of the barriers that women face in Information Technology (IT) in general. However, this hypothesis would need further studies to be discussed.

Fig. 3: The relationship between the most recurrent themes of RQ3 and the demographics of our participants.